

ISic3664

I.Sicily inscription 3664

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia, Villa Whittaker, inventory 756

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108280

1. Nice

2. sal[v]e/

3.

4. Plania

5. vale

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 108280

Bibliography

Gabrics, E. 1929. Stele sepolcrali di Lilibeo a forma di Heroon. *Monumenti Antichi*.

33: 41-60. At 59-60

Bisi, A.M. 1970. Influenze italiote e siceliote sull'arte tardo-punica. Le stele funerarie di Lilibeo. *Archeologia Classica*. 22: 92-130. At 106 no.15 tav.53.1

Vento, M. 2000. Le stele dipinte di Lilibeo. Marsala. At 76-78 tav.37-39

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